

DESIRABLE CHARACTERISTICS OF DATA REPOSITORIES FOR FEDERALLY FUNDED RESEARCH			SPD-41a Appendix D and elsewhere	Answer	Explanation
Organizational Infrastructure	Free and Easy Access	The repository provides broad, equitable, and maximally open access to datasets and their metadata free of charge in a timely manner after submission, consistent with legal and policy requirements related to maintaining privacy and confidentiality, Tribal and national data sovereignty, and protection of sensitive data.	Open Accessibility: The repository provides broad, equitable, and maximally open access to datasets and their metadata free of charge in a timely manner after submission, consistent with legal and policy requirements related to maintaining privacy and confidentiality, tribal and national data sovereignty, and protection of sensitive data. The data will be accessible to the public (lay and scientific) without preapproval.		
	Clear Use Guidance	The repository ensures datasets are accompanied by documentation describing terms of dataset access and use (e.g., reuse licenses and need for approval by a data use committee).	Documentation: The repository will include documentation for its holdings, such as a description of the data, user guides, and descriptions of any calibrations. Documentation will aspire to be broadly accessible and comprehensible to any member of the public with a college degree.		
	Risk Management	The repository has documented capabilities for ensuring that administrative, technical, and physical safeguards are employed to comply with applicable confidentiality, risk management, and continuous monitoring requirements for sensitive data.	Risk Management: The repository has documented capabilities for ensuring that administrative, technical, and physical safeguards are employed to comply with applicable confidentiality, risk management, and continuous monitoring requirements for sensitive data.		
	Retention Policy	The repository provides documentation on policies for data retention.	Retention Policy: The repository provides documentation on policies for data retention.		
	Long-term Organizational Sustainability	The repository has a plan for long-term management of data, including maintaining integrity, authenticity, and availability of datasets; has contingency plans to ensure data are available and maintained during and after unforeseen events.	Sustainability: The repository has plans for long-term management of the data.		
Digital Object Management	Unique Persistent Identifiers	The repository assigns a dataset a citable, unique persistent identifier (PID or DPI), such as a digital object identifier (DOI), to support data discovery, reporting (e.g., of research progress), and research assessment (e.g., identifying the outputs of Federally funded research). The unique PID points to a persistent location that remains accessible even if the dataset is de-accessioned or no longer available.	Citable: The repository will ensure that data are citable through the use of unique persistent identifiers.		
	Metadata	The repository ensures datasets are accompanied by metadata to enable discovery, reuse, and citation of datasets, using schema that are appropriate to, and ideally widely used across, the communities that the repository serves.	Searchability: The repository will ensure that data are searchable, with descriptive metadata being provided along with the data collections.		
	Curation and Quality Assurance	The repository provides or facilitates expert curation and quality assurance to improve the accuracy and integrity of datasets and metadata.	Curation: The repository provides or facilitates expert curation and quality assurance to improve the accuracy and integrity of datasets and metadata.		
	Broad and Measured Reuse	The repository ensures datasets are accompanied by metadata that describe terms of reuse and provides the ability to measure attribution, citation, and reuse of data (e.g., through assignment of adequate and openly accessible metadata and unique PIDs).	---		

	Common Format	The repository allows datasets and metadata to be accessed, downloaded, or exported from the repository in widely used, preferably non-proprietary, formats consistent with standards used in the disciplines the repository serves.	Standardization: The repository will require that data products be submitted in standardized, discipline-appropriate formats and file types.		
	Provenance	The repository has mechanisms in place to record the origin, chain of custody, version control, and any other modifications to submitted datasets and metadata.	Provenance: The repository will ensure that data have configuration control and traceability of changes.		
Technology	Authentication	The repository supports authentication of data submitters. The repository has technical capabilities that facilitate associating submitter PIDs with those assigned to their deposited digital objects, such as datasets.	Authentication: The repository supports authentication of data submitters. The repository has technical capabilities that facilitate associating submitter PIDs with those assigned to their deposited digital objects, such as datasets.		
	Long-term Technical Sustainability	The repository has a plan for long-term management of data, building on a stable technical infrastructure and funding plans.	Sustainability: The repository has plans for long-term management of the data.		
	Security and Integrity	The repository has documented measures in place to meet well established cybersecurity criteria for preventing unauthorized access to, modification of, or release of data, with levels of security that are appropriate to the sensitivity of data (e.g., the NIST Cybersecurity Framework: https://www.nist.gov/cyberframework).	Secure: The repository has documented measures in place to meet well established cybersecurity criteria for preventing unauthorized access to, modification of, or release of data, with levels of security that are appropriate to the sensitivity of data.		
Other	(Not included in the White House policy)		Preeminence: The repository should be considered by its user community as the "standard" repository for the subfield.		
			Independence: The repository should be managed separately from the individual laboratory/mission that is the major data provider.		
			Certified: The properties of the repository should be certified by a recognized, independent group that will attest to the qualities of the repository.		
			Peer Review: The repository should conduct independent peer reviews of data to assess usability and completeness of data packages.		
			Public Review: The repository should provide quality control metrics for completeness and quality. To bring in human validations, social ranking/usage of the data could substitute for peer review.		
			Repositories designated as appropriate for archiving of SMD-funded scientific information shall align, to the extent practicable, to the National Science and Technology Council document entitled Desirable Characteristics of Data Repositories for Federally Funded Research (see blocks above).	-	(see above)
		SMD-funded repositories shall comply, as appropriate, with standards for accessibility for all electronic and information technology to people with disabilities.			

		<p>SMD-funded repositories shall comply, to the extent practicable, with a principle of non-discriminatory data access so that all users will be treated equally. Any variation in accessibility of SMD data will result solely from the capability, equipment, and connectivity of the user.</p>		
		<p>SMD funded repositories should have an Authorization to Operate (ATO) from NASA. If a designated repository is externally managed and not part of NASA network boundary, then there should be a Memorandum of Understanding signed by NASA and the external party about how science information would be shared.</p>		